

A Knowledge-Based Approach to Increase the Uptake of the Influenza Vaccine in Pregnancy

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Background

- Nationally, only 49% of pregnant patients received the influenza vaccine during the 2021-2022 influenza season, a 6% drop from the previous season
- Unvaccinated pregnant patients face a six times higher risk of complications
- Vaccinated pregnant patients see less fetal complications and hospitalizations compared to unvaccinated pregnant patients
- Vaccination of the patient offers protection to infants until they can receive immunization
- Although the influenza vaccine is considered safe and effective in all trimesters, barriers exist, such as vaccine hesitancy, lack of vaccine knowledge, and lack of provider recommendation

Problem

January 2022 to December 2022, the influenza season vaccination rate was 18%

During that timeframe, there were 47,264 opportunities to administer the influenza vaccine, with only 8,426 successful vaccinations achieved

Purpose

To educate the obstetrics and gynecology staff on the safety and effectiveness of the influenza vaccine to increase influenza vaccination rates

Methods

- Setting:** An ambulatory clinic in a large tertiary hospital in San Bernardino County, CA
- Design:** Pretest-Post test survey
- Sample:** Eight OB/GYN staff
- Instrument:** 16-question online survey to assess staff knowledge, attitudes toward vaccines, and vaccine recommendation practices
- Intervention:** A 20-minute influenza education PowerPoint
- Data Analysis:** Paired t-test and C-chart

Modified Iowa Model-Revised for Evidence-Based Practice

Results

Mean Pretest and Post Test Results

Limitations

- Small sample size
- Limited generalizability
- Potential bias
- Limited intervention and data collection

Recommendations

- Increase sample size
- Include other clinics within the hospital to increase generalizability
- Longer data collection
- Specify professions when collecting demographic data
- Implement education before the influenza season starts

Conclusion

- Build upon the findings of this project and implement targeted strategies to address persistent barriers to influenza vaccine uptake among pregnant patients
- Implement ongoing staff education, standing orders, and integration of vaccination reminders into routine clinical workflows
- Adopt a comprehensive approach that addresses both provider and patient perspectives and clinics can play a pivotal role in promoting vaccinations as a cornerstone of preventive care during pregnancy

References

